
Stability of Rectangular Tunnels Subjected to Pseudo-static Earthquake Loadings

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Certificate

It is certified that the work contained in this thesis entitled "Stability of Rectangular Tunnels Subjected to Pseudo-static Earthquake Loadings" by "Gowtham G" has been carried out under my supervision and that it has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Jagdish Prasad Sahoo".

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Declaration

This is to certify that the thesis titled “**Stability of Rectangular Tunnels Subjected to Pseudo-static Earthquake Loadings**” has been authored by me. It presents the research conducted by me under the supervision of **Dr. Jagdish Prasad Sahoo**.

To the best of my knowledge, it is an original work, both in terms of research content and narrative, and has not been submitted elsewhere, in part or in full, for a degree. Further, due credit has been attributed to the relevant state-of-the-art and collaborations (if any) with appropriate citations and acknowledgments, in line with established norms and practices.

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Abstract

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The present study considers the seismic stability of square and rectangular tunnels in granular and cohesive-frictional soils, modelled as a Mohr-Coulomb material. The geotechnical stability problem has been solved using the finite element coupled lower bound limit analysis. The earthquake forces have been included using the pseudo-static method that considers a uniform seismic acceleration in terms of the constant seismic acceleration coefficients. The resultant optimization problem was cast as a Second-Order Cone Programming problem. In the current study, the normal stress has been varied along the tunnel perimeter, and the maximum normal stress has been reported as the support pressure. The parametric study assesses the variation of the support pressure with tunnel cover depth, aspect ratio, soil's shear strength parameters, and seismic acceleration coefficients. For both soil conditions, the support pressure increased with the tunnel cover depth, aspect ratio, and seismic acceleration coefficients. But, with an increase in the soil friction angle, the support pressure was found to drop. For cohesive-frictional soil and a constant tunnel depth, the support pressure increased with the soil's unit weight and decreased soil cohesion. The normal stress distribution around the tunnel shifted from symmetric about the tunnel center for a static loading to otherwise for the seismic case. The location of the maximum normal stress on the tunnel perimeter depended on the aspect ratio of the tunnel, among

other problem parameters. For tall and square tunnels, the maximum normal stress occurred on the walls more than on the base and the roof. On the other hand, the collapse of a wide rectangular tunnel was prone to the failure of the roof than the walls and the base. The extent of the plastified region around the tunnel has been studied using the nodal velocity patterns and was dependent on the problem parameters.

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Symbols

B	tunnel width
c	soil cohesion
C	tunnel cover
c_a	soil-tunnel lining interface adhesion
D	tunnel depth
g	acceleration due to gravity
H	total depth of the domain
k_h	coefficient of seismic acceleration in the horizontal direction
k_v	coefficient of seismic acceleration in the vertical direction
N	Number of nodes in the domain
γ	soil's unit weight
δ	friction angle along the soil-tunnel lining interface
σ_n	normal stress
σ_s	support pressure calculated using the non-uniform stress condition
σ_u	support pressure calculated using the uniform stress condition
τ	shear stress
ϕ	internal friction angle of soil

Abbreviations

FE-LB-LA	F inite E lement - L ower B ound - L imit A nalysis
LB	L ower B ound
M-C	M ohr- C oulomb
SOCP	S econd O rders C one P rogramming
UB	U pper B ound

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 General

Our cities are growing at a rapid pace. The need for efficient transportation systems for quick mobility of people and goods is the need of the hour. Due to space constraints, the use of underground space becomes vital. The subterranean space usage is in the form of tunnels that are being used for various purposes like transportation, pipeline and hydro-projects. The process of tunneling involves the advancement of tunnel boring machines that displaces huge volumes of soil. Eventually, the act of tunneling faces stability issues on two fronts - face and peripheral stability of the tunnel cavity. Compressed air or pressurized slurry helps in stabilizing the tunnel face. On the other hand, the peripheral stability is maintained by installing support systems in the form of linings. The materials used for lining range from steel to cast-in-situ concrete to the most common precast concrete liners. The thickness of the lining systems depend on the ultimate stress onto them from the surrounding earth. Hence, the minimum support pressure to be offered by the lining system should be greater than or equal to the maximum stress from the soil tending to collapse. The response of an underground structure to the earthquake motion is completely different than the superstructure. The present thesis evaluates the ultimate support pressure to

be offered by the liner to prevent the collapse of the tunnel periphery for square and rectangular tunnels subjected seismic forces.

The solutions to the geotechnical stability problems can be found using several methods including the limit equilibrium method, slip line method or the method of stress characteristics, and the limit analysis method. Of these, the present study used the lower bound theorem of limit analysis. The limit analysis method stands on two theorems - the *lower bound* (LB) and *upper bound* (UB) theorems. In the method of limit analysis, the stress-strain relations are considered in an idealized manner using the condition of normality or flow rule. Hence, rigorous solutions could be obtained from the limit analysis method. According to the LB method, the collapse load found using the distribution of stress that satisfies the equations of equilibrium, stresses on the boundaries and do not defy the yield criterion will always be less than the actual collapse load. Whereas, according to the UB theorem, the collapse load is obtained from the energy balance between the rate of work done by the external load and the rate of internal dissipation. This is done by assuming a velocity field that satisfies the boundary conditions specifying the velocities, and the compatibility conditions. The collapse load from the upper bound method will be higher than the actual collapse load, and the soil will be in a state of impending plastic flow. Even though the limit analysis theorems provide rigorous lower and upper bounds to the true collapse load, it is difficult to obtain a closed-form solution, or to appropriately assume the stress field or the deformation pattern. Therefore, the finite element technique of discretizing the soil domain was introduced to apply the limit analysis method to problems with complex geometry and loading conditions. The finite element limit analysis along with various mathematical programming techniques have been developed for solving different stability problems in soil mechanics (Lysmer, 1970; Anderheggen and Knöpfel, 1972; Bottero et al., 1980; Pastor and Turgeman, 1982; Sloan, 1988, 1989; Lyamin and Sloan, 2002; Makrodimopoulos and Martin, 2006, 2007; Krabbenhøft et al., 2007; Tang et al., 2014). Another method to solve the stability problem is using the finite element method (elasto-plastic), which involves the knowledge of all the elasticity and plasticity

parameters. Apart from this, the collapse load is determined after computing the entire load-displacement curve in a step-by-step manner. On the other hand, the limit analysis along with the finite element method calculates the collapse load directly without any step-by-step calculation. Hence, using the limit analysis combined with the finite element method and mathematical programming reduces the computational effort to compute the collapse load.

The present thesis attempts to obtain the support pressure required for the seismic stability of square and rectangular tunnels having rounded corners placed in both granular and cohesive-frictional soils. The seismic inertia force has been accounted for using the *pseudo-static method*. The stability problem has been solved using the LB theorem of limit analysis along with the finite element method. Owing to this, the collapse load will always be less than the actual collapse load; thus safer from the design aspect. The research works in the present thesis have been done using the LB limit analysis plus finite element procedure formulated by [Sloan \(1988\)](#). In order to solve the resulting optimization problem, the second-order cone programming procedure, proposed by [Makrodimopoulos and Martin \(2006\)](#), has been utilized. The computations for the works in this thesis have been done using own MATLAB (2022b) codes, and MOSEK Optimization toolbox was used to solve the second-order conic problem.

1.2 Need, Objective and Scope of the present work

The use of underground space in the form of tunnels is crucial for the ever-expanding urban space. The peripheral stability of tunnels to compute the ultimate stress on the tunnel lining is taken up in this thesis. The minimum thickness required for a liner depends on the magnitude of stress that the liner will be subjected to. Therefore, the computing the stress imposed by the surrounding earth on the tunnel lining systems is essential. Hence, the minimum pressure of support to be offered by the liners have to be greater than or equal to the maximum normal stress from the soil. Even though numerous works are

available to calculate the support pressure, the maximum support pressure to be offered to maintain the peripheral stability of square and rectangular tunnels, with rounded corners, subjected to earthquake forces are yet to be explored; which have been discussed as follows focusing on the need, objective and scope of the research work presented in this thesis.

Several researchers have investigated the stability of rectangular tunnels under different soil conditions subjected to static loading ([Assadi and Sloan, 1991](#); [Lyamin et al., 2001](#); [Yang and Yang, 2010](#); [Yamamoto et al., 2011](#); [Abbo et al., 2013](#); [Wilson et al., 2017](#); [Dutta and Bhattacharya, 2019](#); [Ukritchon and Keawsawasvong, 2020](#); [Shiau et al., 2023](#)). These works consider the stress imposed by the soil is uniform throughout the tunnel periphery. In reality, the stress on the tunnel periphery is not uniform, even for static conditions ([Wood, 1975](#); [International-Tunnelling-Association, 2000](#); [Koyama, 2003](#); [Vu et al., 2017](#); [Sahoo and Gowtham, 2023](#)). Therefore, considering the uniformity of stresses is far from reality. There seems to be no study existing that considers the stress variation along the tunnel periphery to be non-uniform. Furthermore, all these works consider the rectangular tunnel opening made by the tunnel boring machine to have sharp corners. In an actual rectangular tunnel boring machine, the corners are smoothed according to the dimensions and aspect ratio of the machine ([Li, 2017](#)). Therefore, a study is needed to compute the non-uniform variation in the normal stress around the rectangular tunnel with smoothed corners.

[Wang et al. \(2001\)](#) examined the damages caused by the 1999 Chi-Chi earthquake to the tunnels in Taiwan and reported that the lining cracks were the major form of tunnel destruction. [Konagai et al. \(2005\)](#) stated that at some locations of the Uonama tunnel, the steel reinforcements were exposed due to tunnel lining collapse caused by the 2004 Mid-Niigata Prefecture earthquake. The seismic damage caused by the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake to the mountain tunnels in the Dujiangyan Wenchuan highway located in China was extensively studied by [Li \(2012\)](#). It was stated that the main characteristic of lining damage was the simultaneous collapse of the surrounding rock and the lining, which

led to complete tunnel obstruction. Thus, tunnel lining failure has been reported as one of the most frequent forms of earthquake-induced tunnel damage. It is evident that the major form of tunnel damage is due to tunnel lining collapse; hence computing the stresses received by the tunnel periphery from the adjoining ground subjected to seismic activity is critical in safe tunnel design. While the static tunnel stability results are available, the seismic stability of square and rectangular tunnels needs more attention.

In the present thesis, it is aimed to develop solutions for estimating the support pressure required to maintain the stability of square and rectangular tunnels with rounded corners subjected to earthquake loading. Two soil conditions were considered: granular and cohesive-frictional soil. For both the cases, the soil has been considered to be isotropic, homogeneous, and dry. Further, the ground surface was considered to be stress free and perfectly horizontal. The maximum normal stress found from the non-uniform stress variation along the tunnel periphery is reported as the ultimate support pressure to be offered by the lining systems. The seismic inertia forces were accounted for using the pseudo-static method in both horizontal and vertical directions. The support pressure has been presented as a function of tunnel cover depth, tunnel width-to-depth ratio, shear strength parameters of the soil, and the pseudo-static acceleration coefficients. The present thesis furnishes rigorous numerical solutions in the form of non-dimensional charts that can be used readily by the practicing engineers to design the support systems for the tunnel.

1.3 Organization of the thesis

The thesis has been organized into eight different chapters. The present chapter, Chapter 1, introduces the thesis with a brief review of the problems solved in this thesis along with discussing the need, objective and scope of the work carried out in the present thesis.

Chapter 2 starts with a brief review of the progress made in the numerical framework of lower bound limit analysis with the aid of finite elements and various mathematical programming tools. The chapter continues to review the literature available for the stability of square and rectangular tunnels under static and seismic loading conditions.

In chapter 3 details the framework of lower bound limit analysis combined with the finite elements with the second-order cone programming have been presented.

Chapters 4 and 5 furnishes the rigorous solutions, from the present study, for the seismic stability of square and rectangular tunnels with rounded corners in granular and $c-\phi$ soils, respectively.

Chapter 6 lists the important conclusions draw from the thesis, and chapter 7 explores the possible future enhancements that could be made to the present work.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

In the present thesis, the problem of rectangular tunnels' stability under seismicity has been solved numerically using the lower bound limit analysis method. The limit analysis technique is a rational tool to compute the collapse load of a structure involving material plasticity. The two theorems of limit analysis, the lower and upper bound theorems (LB and UB, respectively), stem from the remarkable works of [Drucker et al. \(1951\)](#) and [Hill \(1998\)](#). The classical method of LB limit analysis involves assuming a suitable statically admissible stress field and then computing the collapse load for the problem. On the other hand, the UB limit analysis requires a predefined kinematically admissible collapse pattern to determine the collapse load. The accuracy of the bound solutions from its classical application depends on the closeness of the assumed stress field or the collapse pattern to the reality. Moreover, for problems with complicated geometry and loading, finding the appropriate stress field or the collapse pattern is difficult. Therefore, the bound theorems have been discretized from its continuous form using the finite element technique. The developments in optimization techniques along with the robustness in the conjunction of finite elements with limit analysis fueled several researchers to obtain rigorous bound

solutions for problems with complex geometry and loading conditions ([Lysmer, 1970](#); [Anderheggen and Knöpfel, 1972](#); [Bottero et al., 1980](#); [Pastor and Turgeman, 1982](#); [Sloan, 1988, 1989](#); [Sloan and Kleeman, 1995](#); [Lyamin and Sloan, 2002](#); [Makrodimopoulos and Martin, 2006, 2007](#); [Krabbenhøft et al., 2007](#); [Tang et al., 2014](#)). Section 2.2 discusses, in brief, the contributions made by several researchers to the development of the finite element LB limit analysis (FE-LB-LA) and various optimization techniques.

The stability of tunnels is ensured by provision of stable support pressure systems in the form of tunnel lining. For a stable tunnel lining design, the stress experienced by the tunnel lining along its perimeter has to be computed. The ultimate support pressure to be offered by a tunnel lining to withstand the soil stresses, for square and rectangular tunnels, has been computed by various researchers ([Assadi and Sloan, 1991](#); [Lyamin et al., 2001](#); [Yang and Yang, 2010](#); [Yamamoto et al., 2011](#); [Abbo et al., 2013](#); [Wilson et al., 2017](#); [Dutta and Bhattacharya, 2019](#); [Ukritchon and Keawsawasvong, 2020](#); [Shiau et al., 2023](#)). They considered the soil to be static and the tunnels edges to be sharp. It has been observed that the response of underground structures to seismic motion is different compared to the superstructures. Few studies are available to assess the stability of square and rectangular tunnels under seismicity ([Cilingir and Madabhushi, 2011](#); [Tsinidis et al., 2016](#); [Tsinidis, 2017](#)). A brief review of the works related to the experimental and numerical stability of square and rectangular tunnels has been provided in section 2.3.

2.2 Review of literature related to FE-LB-LA

2.2.1 Anderheggen and Knöpfel (1972)

[Anderheggen and Knöpfel \(1972\)](#) used the finite element method to find the lower and upper limit of the collapse load for general two and three-dimensional bodies. A rigid-ideal plastic material was assumed to facilitate direct computation of the collapse loads. The yield criterion was linearized using a regular polygon to produce linear inequality

constraints. The resulting optimization problem, maximizing for the lower bound and minimizing for the upper bound, was solved using the revised simplex algorithm. Finally, the developed numerical procedure was used to solve plate stretching and bending problems.

2.2.2 Bottero et al. (1980)

Bottero et al. (1980) solved the optimization problem involving linear constraints resulting from the finite element application to the lower and upper bound theorems for geotechnical problems. The soil was discretized using triangular elements, and the stresses (velocities) were allowed to vary linearly within each element. The Mohr-Coulomb (M-C) yield criterion was linearized to formulate the linear programming problem. Further, the method's efficacy was validated by solving classical geotechnical problems like determining the ultimate bearing capacity of strip footing and the ultimate pull-out load of foundations (trapezoidal, rectangular, and floor slabs) and the stability of slopes and vertical cuts in undrained clay.

2.2.3 Pastor and Turgeman (1982)

The FE-LB-LA procedure developed for plane-strain conditions by Bottero et al. (1980) was extended to the axisymmetric problems by Pastor and Turgeman (1982). The stresses were allowed to vary linearly within the triangular element, and the M-C and von Mises yield criteria were linearized. The stability of circular excavations and the problem of cylinder compression (triaxial tests) were analyzed using this.

2.2.4 Sloan (1988)

Similar to Bottero et al. (1980), Sloan (1988) proposed the numerical technique of applying FE-LB-LA method in soil mechanics. The soil domain was discretized using linear

triangular elements. Unlike the previous study (Bottero et al., 1980), Sloan (1988) allowed the statically admissible discontinuities along the shared element edges. The M-C yield condition was linearized using a p -sided polygon. Thus, the resulting optimization problem was a linear programming problem solved using an active set algorithm. This algorithm was reportedly more efficient than the traditional or revised simplex methods.

2.2.5 Lyamin and Sloan (2002)

The disadvantage of linearizing the non-linear yield criteria, like the M-C yield criterion, in FE-LB-LA was addressed by Lyamin and Sloan (2002). The M-C yield criterion was smoothed using a hyperbolic approximation, and the resulting non-linear optimization problem was solved using the fast quasi-Newton method. The superiority of non-linear programming over linear programming was established by applying the developed technique to various geotechnical problems.

2.2.6 Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006)

Unlike Lyamin and Sloan (2002), Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006) used the efficient interior-point algorithm developed for the second-order conic optimization in solving FE-LB-LA problems. Even though the method is applicable only for those yield criteria that can be modeled as a quadratic cone (like Drucker-Prager and M-C), the smoothing of the yield function is avoided. It was reported that the time to solve a Second-Order Cone Programming (SOCP) problem reduces, thus allowing for a more fine discretization. Using finer meshes will lead to a strict lower bound for the true collapse load, thus improving the solutions. The SOCP problem was solved using the commercially available MATLAB toolbox package MOSEK which implements the interior-point algorithm.

2.2.7 Krabbenhøft et al. (2007)

Krabbenhøft et al. (2007) discussed the types of yield criteria that can be cast as conic constraints. The M-C yield function in three dimensions was modeled as a conic constraint using a set of positive-definite cones. Like Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006), the procedure given by Krabbenhøft et al. (2007) does not require any smoothening of the yield function, and the conic program was solved using the MOSEK toolbox. The efficiency of the proposed method was studied by applying it to determine (i) the bearing capacity of circular and square footings on frictional soils, and (ii) the stability of the conical excavations in cohesive-frictional soils.

2.2.8 Tang et al. (2014)

Tang et al. (2014) proposed the lower bound limit analysis formulation of an axisymmetric problem using the SOCP technique. The M-C yield function was expressed as a three-dimensional quadratic conic constraint at each node in the domain. The efficiency of the procedure was validated with the available solutions using the linear programming method to determine the ultimate bearing capacity of the circular footings on cohesive-frictional soils. Furthermore, the numerical procedure was used to obtain the solutions for the uplift capacity of single and multi-plate helical anchors in purely cohesive clay.

2.3 Review of literature related to stability of rectangular tunnels

2.3.1 Assadi and Sloan (1991)

Assadi and Sloan (1991) studied the stability of shallow square tunnels placed in undrained clay using the finite element limit analysis by both the lower and upper bound theorems. The soil was discretized using the linear triangular elements, and the linearized Tresca

yield criterion was used. Furthermore, the upper bound results were also obtained using the rigid sliding block mechanism. The stability of the square tunnel under active (tunnel collapse) and passive (blow-out collapse) failure conditions were addressed. The stability number reported considered the presence of ground surcharge, σ_s .

2.3.2 Lyamin et al. (2001)

The stability of square tunnels placed in cohesive-frictional soil was studied using the limit analysis plus finite elements (lower and upper bound methods) by [Lyamin et al. \(2001\)](#). Similar to [Assadi and Sloan \(1991\)](#), the soil was discretized using the linear triangular elements, and the linear programming technique was used for optimization. Here, the soil was assumed to follow the M-C yield criterion. Moreover, the stability results were validated using the rigid block mechanism. Unlike [Assadi and Sloan \(1991\)](#), [Lyamin et al. \(2001\)](#) studied only the active failure of the square tunnel and ground surcharge was not considered.

2.3.3 Yang and Yang (2010)

The support pressure required for a shallow square tunnel subjected to a ground surcharge and placed in a homogeneous, isotropic, cohesive frictional soil was studied by [Yang and Yang \(2010\)](#). The stability analysis was done using the conventional upper bound method, that is, by using a rigid block failure mechanism and by the finite element upper bound limit analysis. The M-C yield criterion was used along with the linear programming technique. At the end of this study, it was found that a shallow square tunnel's stability depends on the cover depth and soil friction angle.

2.3.4 Cilingir and Madabhushi (2011)

[Cilingir and Madabhushi \(2011\)](#) studied the effect of depth of the tunnel on the seismic response of shallow square tunnels placed in dry sand using dynamic centrifuge tests.

The finite element analysis of the tunnel model was also performed by adopting a non-associative and hardening M-C yield criterion. Rayleigh damping was used for simulating the material damping characteristics. The study found that the tunnel depth does not affect the failure mechanism but significantly influences the amplification of seismic waves from bedrock to the ground surface, dynamic earth pressure, and bending moment in the tunnel lining. Furthermore, the effect of tunnel's lining was also included in the study. The shallow tunnel was found to amplify the seismic acceleration more than the deep tunnel. Also, dynamic earth pressure for the deep tunnel was higher than that of the shallow tunnel. Finally, the tunnel crown deforms more in the case of deep tunnels than the shallower ones.

2.3.5 Yamamoto et al. (2011)

The magnitude of uniform ground surcharge that a shallow square tunnel in cohesive-frictional soil can withstand without collapse was studied by [Yamamoto et al. \(2011\)](#). The LB and UB methods were used with the finite element discretization technique. Moreover, rigid block failure mechanisms were also proposed. The soil followed perfect plasticity, the associated flow rule, and the M-C yield criterion. The results, which include the effect of tunnel lining-soil roughness, were presented in the non-dimensional form. The ultimate surcharge that the tunnel can carry increases with the friction angle of soil. It was reported that the square tunnels could withstand lower surcharge magnitudes than their circular counterparts. Finally, a design equation was proposed based on the average values of LB and UB.

2.3.6 Abbo et al. (2013)

The stability of wide rectangular tunnels in purely cohesive soil was studied by [Abbo et al. \(2013\)](#) using the limit analysis combined with finite element method. The soil was presumed to be homogeneous, isotropic, and obey the Tresca yield criterion. The second-order conic programming was used for optimization. The stability of the wide rectangular

tunnels was expressed in terms of stability number that also considers the effect of ground surcharge. It was found that the stability of the tunnel reduces as its width increases. For tunnels with higher cover depth, the effect of width on the stability diminishes. For square tunnels with lower cover depth, it was found that the tunnel collapse mechanism involves the collapse of the roof and wall of the tunnel. Whereas, for a wide rectangular tunnel at a lower cover depth, the tunnel roof contributed to the collapse mechanism rather than other elements. For tunnels with a higher cover depth, it was noticed that the collapse mechanisms involved the base heave and roof and wall movement, similar to tunnels with a lower cover depth, and the width did not have a significant influence on the failure mechanism.

2.3.7 Tsinidis et al. (2016)

[Tsinidis et al. \(2016\)](#) performed the dynamic centrifuge study to study the seismic response of a flexible, square tunnel embedded in dry sand. A square aluminum tube was used to model the tunnel. Apart from this, a full-scale dynamic finite element analysis was also carried out. The results from the numerical and experimental analyses were validated. The numerical model was then used to study the effects of lining rigidity on the seismic response of the square tunnel. It was found that the results from three and two (plane-strain) dimensional analyses agreed well, and hence the use of plane-strain analysis was deemed sufficient. There existed a rocking vibration mode for flexible tunnels and racking deformations. The racking deformation was found to reduce with an increase in lining rigidity. The dynamic axial force in the lining was affected more by the conditions prevalent along the interface of soil and tunnel lining than the lining bending moment.

2.3.8 Tsinidis (2017)

The response of a rectangular tunnel embedded in uniform granular soil was numerically evaluated by [Tsinidis \(2017\)](#) using the finite element procedure. The effect of parameters like the relative stiffness between the soil and the tunnel lining, the interface conditions

(no or full slip), soil and input motion properties, and the tunnel size, aspect ratio, and depth were discussed. The results were presented as racking ratio-flexibility ratio (R-F) relations, dimensionless rocking-flexibility ratio relations, dynamic earth pressure, shear stresses, and bending moments. It was found that the rectangular tunnel exhibited both racking and rocking mode of deformation under transverse ground motion. The roof and wall slabs were found to deform inward (towards the tunnel's center), and this effect was noticeable for a flexible tunnel lining. The racking deformation was amplified when the soil was modeled as an elastic medium, and a flexible tunnel was considered. The material and geometrical non-linearities shifted the rotation pole from the tunnel section's centroid. The rotation of the tunnel section was found to increase for lower aspect ratios. Similarly, the consequence of these parameters on the dynamic earth pressure, shear stress, and bending moments was discussed.

2.3.9 Wilson et al. (2017)

Similar to [Abbo et al. \(2013\)](#), [Wilson et al. \(2017\)](#) analyzed the stability of rectangular tunnels placed in heterogeneous undrained clay using the finite element limit analysis technique. The lower and upper bound methods were used apart from proposing solutions using the rigid block mechanism. The heterogeneity in the soil's undrained shear strength was considered a linearly varying function of depth from the ground surface. The collapse patterns were observed to align with that reported by [Abbo et al. \(2013\)](#). The collapse of the tunnel roof and walls contributed to the collapse pattern for a narrow and shallow tunnel. On the other hand, at the same cover depth, a square and wide rectangular tunnel's collapse was confined to the roof collapse. For a relatively deep tunnel and any aspect ratio, the failure around the tunnel involved all the components - base heave and roof and wall collapse.

2.3.10 Dutta and Bhattacharya (2019)

Dutta and Bhattacharya (2019) analyzed the stability of rectangular tunnels placed in granular soil. The FE-LB-LA and SOCP were used. The support pressure was found for both the rough and smooth tunnel interfaces. The support pressure required for a wider tunnel was found to be higher than that for a square tunnel.

2.3.11 Ukritchon and Keawsawasvong (2020)

Ukritchon and Keawsawasvong (2020) analyzed the stability of unlined square tunnels in fully cohesive soils using the FE-LB-LA. The undrained clay was assumed to follow the Davis-Christian elliptical yield criterion (Davis and Christian, 1971), thus modeling clay's anisotropy and heterogeneity in undrained shear strength (s_u). The yield function depended on the undrained shear strengths from the plane strain extension ($s_{u_{PSE}}$), plane strain compression ($s_{u_{PSC}}$), and direct shear strength ($s_{u_{DSS}}$) tests. The undrained shear strength in plane strain compression was varied linearly along with depth, the intercept at the ground surface being $s_{u_{PSC0}}$ and the slope being ρ . The stability of the unlined tunnel was found by maximizing the surcharge σ_s that can be applied on the ground surface when the tunnel was subjected to a known stress of σ_t along its periphery. Stability charts were proposed in terms of the stability factor $(\sigma_s - \sigma_t) / s_{u_{PSC0}}$, and other material and geometry parameters. Based on the results, statistical analysis was done to propose a new design equation for the undrained stability of unlined square tunnels. The stability number was found to vary non-linearly with the tunnel cover depth and soil anisotropy parameter. On the other hand, the stability factor was found to vary linearly with the overburden pressure and the gradient ρ of $s_{u_{PSC}}$.

2.3.12 Shiau et al. (2023)

Shiau et al. (2023) developed a design equation for the stability of square box culverts similar to Terzaghi's bearing capacity equation. The study presented charts and tables

for the stability factors for cohesion (F_c), surcharge (F_s), and unit weight (F_γ). The cohesion stability factor (F_c) was calculated by assuming no ground surcharge ($\sigma_s = 0$) and the soil is weightless ($\gamma = 0$). Similarly, other factors were found by making the other two parameters zero. The analysis was done using both the lower and upper-bound limit analysis methods and the adaptive finite element technique. The stability factors were a function of tunnel cover depth and friction angle of soil. Finally, a design example was also presented to showcase the use of the design equation and charts in finding the support pressure required for the stability of the square box culvert.

2.4 Summary

The present chapter provides an overview of prior research pertinent to the subsequent chapters. This chapter summarizes the utilization of limit analysis in conjunction with finite element formulation and diverse optimization techniques for addressing a range of stability issues in geotechnical engineering.

Chapter 3

Finite element lower bound limit analysis

3.1 Introduction

The plastic bounding theorems stem from the primary contributions of [Drucker et al. \(1951\)](#); [Drucker \(1953\)](#) and [Hill \(1998\)](#). The limit analysis uses the plastic bounding theorems to find the bounds for the collapse load for any structure. The method is based on the following assumptions ([Chen, 1975](#)):

- The material follows perfect plastic behavior implying uncontained plastic flow after the yield stress.
- The yield surface is convex, and the normality condition (associated flow rule) holds.
- The virtual work equations are applicable under insignificant changes in the geometry at the limit load.

For a body made of an *ideal material*, following the above properties, the *lower bound* and *upper bound* theorems have been proposed (Drucker, 1953) to find the rigorous bounds for the collapse load.

In this thesis, the LB limit theorem is used to compute the lower bound to the true collapse load of the structure. The lower bound theorem is based on finding a statically admissible stress field. The field of stress that satisfies the equilibrium equations and stress boundary conditions and adheres to the yield function anywhere within the domain is termed the *statically admissible stress field*.

Consider a rigid-perfectly plastic body of domain Ω , bounded by a closed surface Γ . Let $\Gamma = \Gamma_u \cup \Gamma_t$, where Γ_u refers to the portion of the surface Γ on which the displacements \mathbf{u} are specified. Similarly, let Γ_t refer to the part of Γ on which the surface traction \mathbf{t} are specified. Let $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$ for conciseness.

The LB theorem states that, *the loads found from a stress field $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ that satisfies the equilibrium equations, traction boundary conditions on the traction boundary Γ_t , and nowhere violates the assumed yield function $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma})$ will be less than the true collapse load for the structure.* The above requirements can be mathematically stated as,

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{b} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{t} \quad \text{in } \Gamma_t \quad (3.1b)$$

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) \leq 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (3.1c)$$

Here, $\nabla = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mathbf{k}$ in rectangular Cartesian coordinate system, and \mathbf{n} is the unit outward normal on Γ_t .

The above equations (Eq. 3.1) lead to an infinite-dimensional optimization problem that is difficult to solve analytically, especially for complex geometry and complicated loading. Therefore, discretizing the soil by any numerical procedure, like the finite element method, will be helpful to convert Eq. 3.1 to a set of matrix constraints and find the lower bound numerically. Using finite elements to find the lower bound to the actual collapse load was introduced by [Lysmer \(1970\)](#). Based on the formulation by [Lysmer \(1970\)](#), [Anderheggen and Knöpfel \(1972\)](#) and [Bottero et al. \(1980\)](#) extended the application of finite element technique to find the collapse load of classical geotechnical problems. [Sloan \(1988\)](#) proposed a working algorithm for using the lower bound theorem along with the finite element discretization technique with the allowance of statically admissible discontinuities along the edges of adjacent elements. In all the above studies, the constraint posed by the yield criterion is a non-linear inequality constraint (Eq. 3.1), which was linearized using a p -sided polygon by [Sloan \(1988\)](#). From Eq. 3.1, the yield criterion poses a non-linear inequality constraint for the optimization problem. In all the above studies, the non-linear yield function was linearized by approximating it by a p -sided polygon, thus solving a linear programming problem. This approximation was partially eliminated by the non-linear approximation of the yield function by [Lyamin and Sloan \(2002\)](#). Still, the formulation of [Lyamin and Sloan \(2002\)](#) required the differentiability of the yield function for the optimization process. An alternative approach to efficiently solve the optimization problems with convex yield criterion was proposed by [Makrodimopoulos and Martin \(2006\)](#) and [Krabbenhöft et al. \(2007\)](#) using the Second-Order Cone Programming (SOCP) technique which neither approximates the yield function nor requires the differentiability requirement. Moreover, the SOCP problem can be solved efficiently using the MOSEK Optimization toolbox for MATLAB.

The present chapter details the procedure for the finite element limit analysis method by the LB theorem to assess the stability of plane-strain tunnels in geotechnical materials following the Mohr-Coulomb yield condition. The pre-processing codes, like the

finite element discretization and creation of constraint matrices, were written in MATLAB (R2022b). The SOCP optimization was performed in MATLAB using the MOSEK (2017) Optimization Toolbox.

3.2 Lower bound finite element limit analysis formulation

3.2.1 Finite element discretization

The soil is discretized into three noded, linear triangular elements. A typical element is shown in Fig. 3.1. At each node, three unknown stresses exist: σ_x , σ_z , and τ_{xz} . The node numbers for the nodes are given such that they are unique to a particular element, as shown in Fig. 3.2. As a result, a node can have the same coordinate despite having different node numbers such that the statically admissible discontinuity shall be allowed along the element edges.

At each node, three unknown stresses have been considered, namely σ_{x_i} , σ_{z_i} , and τ_{xz_i} . Here, σ_{x_i} and σ_{z_i} are the normal stresses along the X and Z directions, respectively, and τ_{xz_i} is the shear stress in the XZ plane.

FIGURE 3.1: Typical triangular element

FIGURE 3.2: Numbering scheme

The elemental stresses can be found using the shape functions for the linear triangular element and the nodal stresses. For an e^{th} element, the elemental stresses can be expressed as a function of nodal stresses as,

$$\sigma_x^e = \sum_{i=1}^3 \widetilde{N}_i \sigma_{x_i} \quad (3.2a)$$

$$\sigma_z^e = \sum_{i=1}^3 \widetilde{N}_i \sigma_{z_i} \quad (3.2b)$$

$$\tau_{xz}^e = \sum_{i=1}^3 \widetilde{N}_i \tau_{xz_i} \quad (3.2c)$$

Here the shape functions, \widetilde{N}_i are given as,

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{N}_1 &= (\chi_1 + \zeta_1 x + \eta_1 z) / 2A_r^e \\ \widetilde{N}_2 &= (\chi_2 + \zeta_2 x + \eta_2 z) / 2A_r^e \\ \widetilde{N}_3 &= (\chi_3 + \zeta_3 x + \eta_3 z) / 2A_r^e \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

In Eq. 3.3, A_r^e is the shape of the e^{th} triangular element = $|\zeta_1\eta_2 - \zeta_2\eta_1|/2$, and χ_i , ζ_i and η_i are given as,

$$\begin{aligned}\chi_1 &= x_2z_3 - x_3z_2; & \zeta_1 &= z_2 - z_3; & \eta_1 &= x_3 - x_2 \\ \chi_2 &= x_3z_1 - x_1z_3; & \zeta_2 &= z_3 - z_1; & \eta_2 &= x_1 - x_3 \\ \chi_3 &= x_1z_2 - x_2z_1; & \zeta_3 &= z_1 - z_2; & \eta_3 &= x_2 - x_1\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

3.2.2 Element equilibrium

The initial condition in obtaining a LB solution is the satisfaction of the equilibrium equation by the stress field within the soil domain. For a two-dimensional problem, the equilibrium equations for an e^{th} element can be written as,

$$\frac{\partial\sigma_x^e}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial\tau_{xz}^e}{\partial z} = b_x^e\tag{3.5a}$$

$$\frac{\partial\tau_{xz}^e}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial\sigma_z^e}{\partial z} = b_z^e\tag{3.5b}$$

In Eq. 3.5, σ_x^e , σ_z^e , and τ_{xz}^e are the stresses calculated for e^{th} element using Eq. 3.2, and b_x^e and b_z^e are the body forces along the X and Z directions, respectively.

For the pseudo-static analysis, the body forces b_x^e and b_z^e can be written as,

$$b_x^e = \gamma k_h\tag{3.6}$$

$$b_z^e = \gamma [1 - k_v]\tag{3.7}$$

Here, k_h and k_v are the seismic acceleration coefficients along the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively, and γ is the unit weight of soil.

By substituting Eq. 3.2 in Eq. 3.5, the equilibrium equations can be expressed in the matrix form as,

$$(\mathbf{A}_{\text{equil}}^e)_{2 \times 9} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^e)_{9 \times 1} = (\mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}}^e)_{2 \times 1} \quad (3.8)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{equil}}^e = \frac{1}{2A_r^e} \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_1 & 0 & \eta_1 & \zeta_2 & 0 & \eta_2 & \zeta_3 & 0 & \eta_3 \\ 0 & \eta_1 & \zeta_1 & 0 & \eta_2 & \zeta_2 & 0 & \eta_3 & \zeta_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^e = \left\{ \sigma_{x_1} \quad \sigma_{z_1} \quad \tau_{xz_1} \quad \sigma_{x_2} \quad \sigma_{z_2} \quad \tau_{xz_2} \quad \sigma_{x_3} \quad \sigma_{z_3} \quad \tau_{xz_3} \right\}^T$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}}^e = \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma k_h \\ \gamma[1 - k_v] \end{Bmatrix}$$

Thus for an element, the equilibrium condition will impose two equality constraints. So, for E number of elements, $2E$ number of equality constraints will be developed.

After imposing the equality constraint for the equilibrium equations on all E elements, assembly is done to compute the global matrices $\mathbf{A}_{\text{equil}}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}}$. These global matrices can be expressed as,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{equil}} = \left[\sum_{e=1}^E \mathbf{A}_{\text{equil}}^e \right]_{2E \times 3N} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}} = \left[\sum_{e=1}^E \mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}}^e \right]_{2E \times 1} \quad (3.10)$$

here, N is the total number of nodes in the finite element mesh, and $N = 3E$.

3.2.3 Statically admissible discontinuity

Using statically admissible discontinuities along the element edges has been known to reduce the error between the true collapse load and its lower bound estimate (Drucker, 1953; Lysmer, 1970; Sloan, 1988). Hence, additional constraints must be imposed to allow the statically admissible stress discontinuities at the edges of the adjacent triangular elements. A statically admissible discontinuity permits the continuity of shear and normal stress components and allows the jump in tangential stresses.

FIGURE 3.3: Statically admissible stress discontinuity

From Fig. 3.3, for the discontinuity to be statically admissible, the following constraints, in terms of normal stress σ_n and shear stress τ_{xz} , are imposed:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{n1}^a &= \sigma_{n2}^b; & \sigma_{n3}^a &= \sigma_{n4}^b \\ \tau_1^a &= \tau_2^b; & \tau_3^a &= \tau_4^b \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_n &= \sin^2 \beta \sigma_x + \cos^2 \beta \sigma_z - \sin 2\beta \tau_{xz} \\ \tau &= -0.5 \sin 2\beta \sigma_x + 0.5 \sin 2\beta \sigma_z + \cos 2\beta \tau_{xz} \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

Substituting Eq. 3.12 in Eq. 3.11, the constraints for imposing statically admissible discontinuity, concerning Fig. 3.3, can be expressed in matrix form as,

$$\left(\mathbf{A}_{\text{stat}}^{\text{d}}\right)_{4 \times 12} \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{d}}\right)_{12 \times 1} = \left(\mathbf{b}_{\text{stat}}^{\text{d}}\right)_{4 \times 1} \quad (3.13)$$

Here,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{stat}}^{\text{d}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_0 & -\mathbf{J}_0 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_0 & -\mathbf{J}_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(\mathbf{J}_0)_{2 \times 3} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin^2 \beta & \cos^2 \beta & \sin 2\beta \\ -0.5 \sin 2\beta & 0.5 \sin 2\beta & 0.5 \cos 2\beta \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{d}} = \left\{ \sigma_1^a \quad \sigma_2^b \quad \sigma_3^a \quad \sigma_4^b \right\}^{\text{T}}$$

$$(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^j)_{3 \times 1} = \left\{ \sigma_{x_i}^j \quad \sigma_{z_i}^j \quad \tau_{xz_i}^j \right\}^{\text{T}} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, 4; j = a, b)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{stat}}^{\text{d}} = \mathbf{0}$$

Hence, if the number of element edges in the mesh is D , there will be $4D$ number of equality constraints. After assembling for all the discontinuities, the global matrices \mathbf{A}_{stat} and \mathbf{b}_{stat} can be expressed as follows,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{stat}} = \left[\sum_{d=1}^D \mathbf{A}_{\text{stat}}^{\text{d}} \right]_{4D \times 3N} \quad (3.14)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{stat}} = \left[\sum_{d=1}^D \mathbf{b}_{\text{stat}}^{\text{d}} \right]_{4D \times 1} \quad (3.15)$$

where D is the total number of stress discontinuities.

3.2.4 Stress boundary conditions

The normal and shear stresses at the j^{th} node of a typical boundary surface bd located at an angle θ from the positive X axis, shown in Fig. 3.4, are given by:

$$\sigma_{n_j} = \sigma_{x_j} \sin^2(\theta) + \sigma_{z_j} \cos^2(\theta) - \tau_{xz_j} \sin(2\theta) \quad (3.16a)$$

$$\tau_j = -0.5\sigma_{x_j} \sin(2\theta) + 0.5\sigma_{z_j} \sin(2\theta) + \tau_{xz_j} \cos(2\theta) \quad (3.16b)$$

FIGURE 3.4: Stress boundary condition at a typical boundary node

The Eq. 3.16 can be expressed in the matrix form at each node on the boundary surface as:

$$\left(\mathbf{A}_{\text{bound}}^{\text{bd}} \right)_{2 \times 3} \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{bd}} \right)_{3 \times 1} = \left(\mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}}^{\text{bd}} \right)_{2 \times 1} \quad (3.17)$$

Here,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{bound}}^{\text{bd}} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin^2 \theta & \cos^2 \theta & -\sin 2\theta \\ -0.5 \sin 2\theta & 0.5 \sin 2\theta & \cos 2\theta \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{bd}} = \left\{ \sigma_{x_j}^{\text{bd}} \quad \sigma_{z_j}^{\text{bd}} \quad \tau_{xz_j}^{\text{bd}} \right\}^{\text{T}}$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}}^{\text{bd}} = \left\{ \sigma_{n_j}^{\text{bd}} \quad \tau_j^{\text{bd}} \right\}^{\text{T}}$$

Thus, two equality constraints are developed for each node on the boundary of specified stresses. The Eq. 3.17 is generated for all the nodes where the stress boundary conditions are prescribed and assembled to create the global boundary condition matrices. The global boundary condition matrices $\mathbf{A}_{\text{bound}}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}}$ are given as:

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{bound}} = \left[\sum_{\text{bd}=1}^{N_b} \mathbf{A}_{\text{bound}}^{\text{bd}} \right]_{2N_b \times 3N} \quad (3.18)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}} = \left[\sum_{\text{bd}=1}^{N_b} \mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}}^{\text{bd}} \right]_{2N_b \times 1} \quad (3.19)$$

where N_b is the number of nodes on the surface in which the stress boundary conditions are prescribed.

3.2.5 Yield criteria

For the stress field to be statically admissible and to provide a lower bound estimate, the stresses should be below the yield surface. In the present study, the soil has been assumed to follow the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion. For the plane-strain condition, the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion applied at the i^{th} node of the domain is given as,

$$\sqrt{(\sigma_{x_i} - \sigma_{z_i})^2 + 4\tau_{xz_i}^2} \leq 2c \cos \phi - (\sigma_{x_i} + \sigma_{z_i}) \sin \phi \quad (3.20)$$

The inequality in Eq. 3.20 can be expressed as a set of second-order conic constraints (Makrodimopoulos and Martin, 2006) by introducing a vector of auxiliary variables, $\Psi = \left\{ \Psi_1 \quad \Psi_2 \quad \Psi_3 \right\}^T$. The elements of the auxiliary variable vector, Ψ , should satisfy the equation of second-order cone, $\Psi_1 \geq \sqrt{\Psi_2^2 + \Psi_3^2}$.

Incorporating the auxiliary variables, Ψ_i , Eq. 3.20 can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} (\sigma_{x_i} + \sigma_{z_i}) \sin \phi + \Psi_1 &= 0 \\ -\sigma_{x_i} + \sigma_{z_i} + \Psi_2 &= 0 \\ -\tau_{xz_i} + \Psi_3 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

Or it can be expressed in the matrix form as,

$$\left(\mathbf{A}_{\text{socp}}^i \right)_{3 \times 3} \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^i \right)_{3 \times 1} + \left(\boldsymbol{\Psi}^i \right)_{3 \times 1} = \left(\mathbf{b}_{\text{socp}}^i \right)_{3 \times 1} \quad (3.22)$$

Here,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{socp}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \phi & \sin \phi & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^i = \left\{ \sigma_{x_i} \quad \sigma_{z_i} \quad \tau_{xz_i} \right\}^T ; \quad \boldsymbol{\Psi}^i = \left\{ \Psi_1^i \quad \Psi_2^i \quad \Psi_3^i \right\}^T ; \quad \mathbf{b}_{\text{socp}}^i = \mathbf{0}$$

At each node, three equality constraints are imposed. Thus, the global matrices to impose the equality constraint on all the nodes can be written as,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{socp}} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{A}_{\text{socp}}^i \right]_{3N \times 3N} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{socp}} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{\text{socp}}^i \right]_{3N \times 1} \quad (3.24)$$

3.2.6 Support system modeling

In the present study, the tunnel support system is modeled using the edges of the elements on the tunnel periphery. The size of elements has been considered small, and the difference in the arc length and the chord length is minimal.

The previous studies ([Assadi and Sloan, 1991](#); [Abbo et al., 2013](#); [Wilson et al., 2015, 2017](#); [Dutta and Bhattacharya, 2019](#)) considered the stresses from the surrounding soil onto the tunnel uniform through the tunnel periphery. For this condition, the following equality constraint was imposed additionally to all the nodes along the tunnel periphery

$$\sigma_u = \sigma_{n_1} = \sigma_{n_2} = \cdots = \sigma_{n_i} = \sigma_{n_{i+1}} = \cdots = \sigma_{n_{N_t}} \quad (3.25)$$

In reality, the pressure exerted on the tunnel periphery is seldom uniform ([Wood, 1975](#); [International-Tunnelling-Association, 2000](#); [Koyama, 2003](#); [Vu et al., 2017](#); [Sahoo and Gowtham, 2023](#)). Therefore, in the present study, the normal stresses along the tunnel periphery are not constrained to be equal, and hence no additional constraint is imposed on the tunnel nodes. The support pressure is calculated as the maximum of all the normal stresses along the tunnel periphery. Mathematically,

$$\sigma_s = \max \left[\sigma_{n_1}, \sigma_{n_2}, \cdots, \sigma_{n_i}, \sigma_{n_{i+1}}, \cdots, \sigma_{n_{N_t}} \right] \quad (3.26)$$

In Eq. 3.25 and Eq. 3.26, σ_{n_i} and $\sigma_{n_{i+1}}$ are the normal stresses exerted by the surrounding soil at the i^{th} and $i+1^{\text{th}}$ nodes, respectively, and N_t is the total number of nodes on the tunnel periphery.

3.2.7 Tunnel lining-soil interface condition

To include the effect of the interface between the tunnel lining and the surrounding soil, the following inequality constraint has to be satisfied at the state of ultimate failure

$$|\tau_{nt}| \leq c_a - \sigma_n \tan \delta \quad (3.27)$$

Eq. 3.27 can also be written as:

$$\tau_{nt} \leq c_a - \sigma_n \tan \delta \quad (3.28a)$$

$$-\tau_{nt} \leq c_a - \sigma_n \tan \delta \quad (3.28b)$$

Here, σ_n is the normal stress at the lining-soil interface, δ and c_a are the interface friction angle and the interface adhesion, respectively.

Eq. 3.27 states that, at the instant of ultimate shear failure, the mobilized shear stress τ_{nt} along the tunnel lining-soil interface is always less than its shear strength. Moreover, the soil movement can be in any direction relative to the tunnel lining. Therefore, the positive and negative signs of shear stress have been considered. It is worth noting that, in Eq. 3.27, the normal pressure is appended with a negative sign due to the sign convention of positive tensile stresses.

Using the definitions of normal and shear stresses (3.12 or 3.16), the matrix form of 3.27 at the i^{th} node on the tunnel lining-soil interface is given as:

$$\left(\mathbf{A}_{\text{int}}^i \right)_{2 \times 3} \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^i \right)_{3 \times 1} \leq \left(\mathbf{b}_{\text{int}}^i \right)_{2 \times 1} \quad (3.29)$$

Here,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{int}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} T_1 + T_2 \\ -T_1 + T_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$T_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \sin 2\theta_i & -0.5 \sin 2\theta_i & -\cos 2\theta_i \end{bmatrix}$$

$$T_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \theta_i & \sin^2 \theta_i & -\sin 2\theta_i \end{bmatrix} \tan \delta$$

Also,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^i = \left\{ \sigma_{x_i} \quad \sigma_{z_i} \quad \tau_{xz_i} \right\}^T$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{int}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} c_{a_i} \\ c_{a_i} \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, c_{a_i} is the adhesion at the i^{th} node; θ_i is the angle made by the line radiating from the tunnel's center to the i^{th} node with the horizontal.

The two equality conditions on a node on the tunnel periphery are applied to all the tunnel nodes to obtain the global matrices for the tunnel-lining interface condition. Thus,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{int}} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}}^i \right]_{2N_t \times 3N} \quad (3.30)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{int}} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \mathbf{b}_{\text{int}}^i \right]_{2N_t \times 1} \quad (3.31)$$

Here, N_t is the total number of nodes on the tunnel periphery.

3.2.8 Objective function

The objective function for the finite element limit analysis problem is the magnitude of the collapse load that needs to be optimized. Therefore, in the present study, the support

pressure to maintain the tunnel's stability at ultimate shear failure is the collapse load (hence the objective function). The objective function is found by integrating the normal stresses along those edges of the elements that constitute the tunnel periphery and is expressed as

$$Q_c = \int_{L_s} \sigma_n ds \quad (3.32)$$

Here, Q_c , L_s , and σ_n are the magnitude of the collapse load per unit length of the tunnel, the perimeter of the tunnel, and the normal stress on the interface.

For a linear triangular element, the stresses vary linearly. Hence, the component of the collapse load for a given side of the element along the tunnel periphery, Q_c^s , can be written as

$$Q_c^s = \frac{l^s}{2} (\sigma_{n_1} + \sigma_{n_2}) \quad (3.33)$$

where σ_{n_1} and σ_{n_2} are the normal stresses on the nodes 1 and 2, respectively, on the side of the element edge of length l^s .

Using the standard expression for normal stress (Eq. 3.16), the Eq. 3.33 can be expressed in matrix form as,

$$\mathbf{Q}_c = (\mathbf{c}^s)^T_{1 \times 6} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^s)_{6 \times 1} \quad (3.34)$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{c}^s &= \frac{l^s}{2} \left\{ \cos^2 \theta_1 \quad \sin^2 \theta_1 \quad -\sin 2\theta_1 \quad \cos^2 \theta_2 \quad \sin^2 \theta_2 \quad -\sin 2\theta_2 \right\}^T \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}^s &= \left\{ \sigma_{x_1}^s \quad \sigma_{z_1}^s \quad \tau_{xz_1}^s \quad \sigma_{x_2}^s \quad \sigma_{z_2}^s \quad \tau_{xz_2}^s \right\}^T \\ \mathbf{Q}_c &= \sum_{s=1}^S Q_c^s \end{aligned}$$

Here, S is the total number of element edges along the tunnel periphery = $N_t/2$.

3.2.9 Formulation of the optimization problem

The second-order cone programming can be stated in its standard form by assembling all the constraint matrices into global matrices for use in MOSEK as,

$$\max \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{x} \quad \text{or} \quad \min -\mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{x} \quad (3.35)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_l \leq \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{B}_u \quad (3.36)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_l \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}_u \quad (3.37)$$

In Eq. 3.35, $\mathbf{c} = \{c_1 \ 0\}^T$, where $c_1 = \sum_{s=1}^S \mathbf{c}^s$ (from Eq. 3.34), and $\mathbf{x} = \{\boldsymbol{\sigma} \ \boldsymbol{\Psi}\}$.

Here,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{3N \times 1} = \left\{ \sigma_{x_1} \ \sigma_{z_1} \ \tau_{xz_1} \ \sigma_{x_2} \ \sigma_{z_2} \ \tau_{xz_2} \ \cdots \ \sigma_{x_N} \ \sigma_{z_N} \ \tau_{xz_N} \right\}^T$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{3N \times 1} = \left\{ \Psi_{11} \ \Psi_{21} \ \Psi_{31} \ \Psi_{12} \ \Psi_{22} \ \Psi_{32} \ \cdots \ \Psi_{1N} \ \Psi_{2N} \ \Psi_{3N} \right\}^T$$

In Eq. 3.36,

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{\text{equil}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{A}_{\text{stat}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{A}_{\text{bound}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{A}_{\text{socp}} & \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}_{(2E+4D+2N_b+3N+2N_t) \times (3N+3N)} \quad (3.38)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_l = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{\text{stat}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{\text{socp}} \\ -\text{inf } \mathbf{I} \end{Bmatrix}_{(2E+4D+2N_b+3N+2N_t) \times (1)} \quad \mathbf{B}_u = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{\text{stat}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{\text{socp}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{\text{int}} \end{Bmatrix}_{(2E+4D+2N_b+3N+2N_t) \times (1)} \quad (3.39)$$

In Eq. 3.38, $\mathbf{A}_{\text{equil}}$, \mathbf{A}_{stat} , $\mathbf{A}_{\text{bound}}$, \mathbf{A}_{socp} , and \mathbf{A}_{int} are the global matrices of each constraint, and they are given by the equations 3.9, 3.14, 3.18, 3.23 and 3.30, respectively. Similarly, $\mathbf{b}_{\text{equil}}$, \mathbf{b}_{stat} , $\mathbf{b}_{\text{bound}}$, \mathbf{b}_{socp} , and \mathbf{b}_{int} are given by the equations 3.10, 3.15, 3.19, 3.24, and 3.31, respectively.

In Eq. 3.37, since no constraint is imposed on the independent variables (i.e., the elements of \mathbf{x}), $\mathbf{b}_l = \mathbf{b}_u = []$.

Also,

\mathbf{I} = Identity matrix,

N = Total number of nodes,

E = Total number of elements,

D = Total number of stress discontinuities,

N_b = Total number of nodes where the stress boundary conditions are specified,

N_t = Total number of nodes on the tunnel periphery,

S = Total number of element edges along the tunnel periphery = $N_t/2$ and

–inf = negative infinity.

In the present study, MATLAB was used to generate the problem variables as sparse matrices, and the SOCP was performed using the MOSEK Optimization toolbox.

3.3 Summary

The chapter discussed the procedure for obtaining the lower bound solution using the finite element discretization of limit analysis for plane strain problems in soil mechanics. The second-order cone programming was used for the optimization of the collapse load. A brief description of the use of MOSEK in solving the second-order cone programming was also made. Even though the chapter discussed the formulation under the prelude of the associated flow rule, procedures were provided to obtain solutions for the materials obeying the non-associated flow rule from the results computed based on the assumptions of the associated flow rule.

Chapter 4

Seismic stability of rectangular tunnels in granular soil

4.1 Introduction

Rapid urbanization demands an increased utilization of the underground space. Nowadays, tunnel construction is increasing. The stability of the tunnel is ascertained by the provision of tunnel lining systems. The design of the tunnel liners requires the knowledge of stresses that get transferred from the surrounding soil to the tunnel. Moreover, unlike the structures above the ground, the seismic design of underground structures is quite different. Application of the finite element limit analysis (lower bound method) to solve the stability of rectangular tunnels in granular soils under static load was done recently by [Dutta and Bhattacharya \(2019\)](#). Furthermore, the response of such structures placed in granular soil subjected to seismic action was evaluated by [Cilingir and Madabhushi \(2011\)](#); [Tsinidis et al. \(2016\)](#); [Tsinidis \(2017\)](#). All the studies consider the tunnel to have sharp corners, but the rectangular tunnel boring machines are manufactured with rounded corners ([Li, 2017](#)). Further, these studies consider that the stress from the soil on to the tunnel lining is uniform throughout the tunnel periphery deviating from the non-uniform distribution of stresses ([Wood, 1975](#); [International-Tunnelling-Association, 2000](#); [Koyama,](#)

2003; Vu et al., 2017). Moreover, the stability of square and rectangular tunnels subjected to seismic forces are yet to be investigated.

Therefore, the present study examines the stability of square and rectangular tunnels with rounded corners located in sand under earthquake loading. The seismic body forces incorporated in the analysis using the pseudo-static method by means of the seismic acceleration coefficients k_h and k_v in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. The lower bound limit analysis theorem along with finite element method was used to obtain the normal stresses along the tunnel periphery and the maximum of these is the minimum pressure required to ensure tunnel stability. The influence of the geometric parameters like the cover depth, aspect ratio, and the seismic acceleration coefficients has been studied along with the collapse pattern and the distribution of normal stress around the tunnel.

4.2 Problem description

The present study analyses the stability of rectangular tunnels of dimensions $B \times D$ placed at a cover depth of C from the ground surface in granular soil, as shown in Fig. 4.1. In the present study, the corner of the tunnel is assumed to be rounded to a depth of d . The soil has a unit weight of γ and a friction angle of ϕ . The soil medium is subjected to horizontal and vertical seismic forces, quantified using the corresponding seismic coefficients k_h and k_v , respectively. The soil is assumed to be dry, homogeneous, and isotropic. The ground follows the associated flow rule and is governed by the Mohr-Coulomb (M-C) yield criterion. Furthermore, the maximum normal stress along the tunnel periphery is the tunnel's support pressure σ_s . The soil properties are assumed not to vary due to seismic forces.

FIGURE 4.1: Problem description

4.3 Problem domain and boundary conditions

Fig. 4.2 shows the problem domain (LMNO) and associated traction boundary conditions. The ground surface, LM, is free of any stresses. Thus, along the ground surface, $\sigma_n = 0$ and $\tau = 0$. Moreover, the other boundaries MN, NO, and OL, were kept far apart such that they do not affect the support pressure values. The analysis used the FE-LB-LA method. The soil domain LMNO (Fig. 4.2) was discretized into three noded triangular elements. A typical finite element mesh used for square tunnels ($B/D = 1$) is shown in Fig. 4.3. The number of elements was found to be dependent on the tunnel cover depth, seismic coefficients, friction angle, and tunnel aspect ratio (B/D).

4.4 Comparison of uniform and non-uniform stress distributions

Fig. 4.4 shows the variation of support pressures with the friction angle with $C/D = 1$, $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, and for $B/D = 0.5, 1$, and 1.5 . Fig. 4.4(a) shows the variation of σ_u based on the uniform stress distribution (Eq. 3.25) and Fig. 4.4(b) shows the variation

FIGURE 4.2: Problem domain and boundary conditions

FIGURE 4.3: Typical finite element mesh for $B/D = 1$

of σ_s based on the non-uniform stress distribution (Eq. 3.26). It is evident that the shear strength of soil increases as ϕ increases, and so the support pressure requirement drops. Also, as B/D increases, the support pressure requirement increases. For given values of B/D and ϕ , the support pressure required to maintain the tunnel stability calculated based on Eq. 3.26 (non-uniform stress distribution) is markedly higher than that from Eq. 3.25. For example, from Fig. 4.4(a), for $B/D = 1$ and $\phi = 25^\circ$, $\sigma_u = 0.44\gamma D$. On the other hand, from Fig. 4.4(b) for the same parameters, the value of the support

pressure considering the non-uniform stress distribution was about $2.52\gamma D$, which is a steep increase by a factor of 5.73. Therefore, considering the maximum normal stress as the support pressure requirement will lead to a conservative tunnel design.

FIGURE 4.4: Comparison of support pressure from the (a) uniform, $\sigma_u/\gamma D$, and (b) non-uniform, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, stress distributions with variations in ϕ and B/D values. Here, $C/D = 1$, $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$.

4.5 Results and Discussion

The stability charts for a rectangular tunnel of width B and depth D regarding the non-dimensional support pressure $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ were generated in the present study. These stability charts show the variation of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ with various parameters like the tunnel cover depth-to-depth ratio (C/D), tunnel aspect ratio (B/D), friction angle of soil (ϕ), and horizontal and vertical seismic acceleration coefficients (k_h and k_v , respectively). The collapse of the rectangular tunnels, with various parametric values, was analyzed using the nodal velocity patterns. Finally, the distributions of the normal stress around the tunnel periphery were also produced considering the account of the parameters.

4.5.1 Parametric study on support pressure

In this subsection, the variation of the support pressure $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ with the interface conditions of the soil-tunnel lining and with other parameters like C/D , B/D , ϕ , k_h and k_v are presented.

4.5.1.1 Effect of soil-tunnel lining interface condition

Fig. 4.5 illustrates the variation of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ with the interface friction angle, expressed in its non-dimensional form as δ/ϕ for $C/D = 1$, $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, and for different ϕ values. The variation is shown for $B/D = 0.5, 1$, and 1.5 in Fig. 4.5(a), (b), and (c), respectively. For fixed values of B/D and ϕ , the value of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ reduces as δ/ϕ increases. This is attributed to increased frictional resistance compared to the amount of shear stress mobilized along the soil-lining interface. Hence, the support pressure requirement drops as the value of the interface friction angle increases. A similar trend was observed for any value of C/D , B/D , and ϕ . For example, referring to Fig. 4.5(b) and for $\phi = 45^\circ$, the value of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ drops almost twice as δ/ϕ increases from zero to one. In another case, for $B/D = 1.5$ and $\phi = 25^\circ$ (Fig. 4.5(c)), the value of σ_s is $2.52\gamma D$ for $\delta/\phi = 0$. Whereas, for the same parameters, $\sigma_s = 1.83\gamma D$ for $\delta/\phi = 1$, which is a drop of almost 55%. In conclusion, considering a smooth interface, given by $\delta/\phi = 0$, leads to a conservative tunnel design. Hence, the forthcoming sections provide the results considering $\delta/\phi = 0$.

4.5.1.2 Effect of tunnel geometric and seismic parameters

Fig. 4.6 shows the effect of k_h , k_v , and ϕ on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ for $C/D = 1$ and 3 , respectively. $B/D = 0.5, 1$, and 1.5 were considered. It is clear from these figures that as the value of the soil friction angle increases, the soil's shear strength increases, and hence the support pressure requirement for the tunnel drops. For instance, from Fig. 4.6(b) ($C/D = 1$ and $B/D = 1$), for $k_h = 0$ and $\phi = 25^\circ$, the value of σ_s is equal to $2.43\gamma D$. On the other hand, $\sigma_s = 0.73\gamma D$ for $\phi = 45^\circ$, which is only 0.3 times the σ_s value for $\phi = 25^\circ$.

FIGURE 4.5: Effect of interface friction angle, expressed as δ/ϕ , over the support pressure $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ for $C/D = 1$ with (a) $B/D = 0.50$, (b) $B/D = 1$, and (c) $B/D = 1.5$. Here $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$.

As the value of k_h increases, the seismic load increases. Similarly, the inclusion of the effect of vertical earthquake acceleration along with the horizontal earthquake acceleration (non-zero values of k_h and k_v) gives a higher support pressure than only the horizontal earthquake acceleration effect. From Fig. 4.6(b) with $\phi = 25^\circ$, $\sigma_s = 2.43\gamma D$ for static case and $\sigma_s = 3.3\gamma D$ for $k_h = 0.3$, $k_v = k_h/2$, which is a surge by 36%. On the other hand, keeping all the other parameters constant, for $k_v = 0$, $\sigma_s = 3.1\gamma D$, a drop by 6.5%. Also, as the value of C/D increases, the overburden to be supported by the tunnel increases. Therefore, the support pressure requirement increases along with C/D . Furthermore, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ increases along with the value of B/D . From figures 4.6(d), (e), and (f), keeping $\phi = 30^\circ$, $k_h = 0.2$, and $k_v = k_h/2$, the values of $\sigma_s = 2.21\gamma D$, $2.4\gamma D$, and $2.7\gamma D$ for $B/D = 0.5$, 1 and 1.5, respectively. Since more soil is removed for the construction of square

and wide rectangular tunnels ($B/D \geq 1$), narrower tunnels ($B/D < 1$) are more stable, requiring lower support pressure, which has already been reported by [Wilson et al. \(2015, 2017\)](#) under static loading condition.

4.5.2 Nodal velocity patterns

The MOSEK solver uses a primal-dual interior point algorithm to solve the SOCP problem, from which both the primal and the dual solutions for the problem can be obtained. Thus, the primal solution provides the nodal stresses, and the dual provides the nodal velocities. Figures 4.7 and 4.8 show typical nodal velocity patterns for various parameters used in this study. Fig. 4.7(a) gives the velocity pattern for $C/D = 1$, $B/D = 1$, $\phi = 25^\circ$ subjected to static loading. Similarly, figures 4.7(b) and 4.7(c) is plotted for $\phi = 25^\circ$ and $\phi = 40^\circ$, respectively, using $C/D = 1$, $B/D = 1$, $k_h = 0.2$, and $k_v = k_h/2$. Since the static loading on the tunnel is symmetric about the vertical through the tunnel center, the velocity pattern is also symmetric about the center. From Fig. 4.7(a), for a square tunnel placed at a relatively shallow depth and subjected to static load, the collapse of the tunnel involves the collapse of the roof, walls, and the heave of tunnel base.

Comparing figures 4.7(a) and 4.7(b), it can be stated that the velocity pattern becomes one-sided due to the effect of seismic loading. From Fig. 4.7(b), even though the seismic collapse of a square tunnel encompasses the tunnel walls, roof and the base heave, the base heave has a higher edge than the others. The base heave is also one-sided due to the seismic forces. When the friction angle of soil increases, the collapse of the tunnel is more confined around the tunnel periphery thus reducing the support pressure requirement. The above statement is evident by comparing the figures 4.7(b) and 4.7(c). Another interesting thing to note is that as ϕ increases, the collapse pattern of the tunnel is more around the tunnel roof and the walls rather than the tunnel bottom. Thus, as ϕ increases, the collapse pattern does not propagate till the tunnel base.

FIGURE 4.6: Variation of $\sigma_s / \gamma D$ with k_h , k_v , and ϕ with $B/D = 0.5, 1, \text{ and } 1.5$ for (a-c) $C/D = 1$, and (d-f) $C/D = 3$

FIGURE 4.7: For $C/D = 1$ and $B/D = 1$, the velocity patterns for (a) static loading with $\phi = 25^\circ$; (b) seismic loading with $\phi = 25^\circ$; and (c) seismic loading with $\phi = 45^\circ$. Here, for the seismic loading, $k_h = 0.2$, $k_v = k_h/2$

FIGURE 4.8: For $C/D = 1$, velocity patterns for $\phi = 30^\circ$, $k_h = 0.3$, and $k_v = k_h/2$ with (a) $B/D = 0.5$, (b) $B/D = 1$, and (c) $B/D = 1.5$

Fig. 4.8 shows the effect of tunnel aspect ratio (B/D) on the velocity distribution under seismic loading for $C/D = 1$. Also, $\phi = 30^\circ$, $k_h = 0.3$, and $k_v = k_h/2$ were used. As the B/D ratio of the tunnel increases, the collapse of the tunnel is found to shift gradually from the walls to the roof of the tunnel. Thus, the collapse of a narrow tunnel (Fig. 4.8(a)) is governed by the collapse of the tunnel wall. Similar to Fig. 4.7(b), in Fig. 4.8(b) the seismic collapse of a square tunnel is dominated by the base heave with considerable contributions from the tunnel wall and roof. For a wide tunnel (Fig. 4.8(c)), the collapse of the roof and the collapse of the base due to heave dominates than the tunnel wall collapse for obvious reasons. Furthermore, from figures 4.7 and 4.8, due to seismic loading, as the soil from the left-hand side of the tunnel moves towards the tunnel, the soil near the ground surface on the right-hand side of the tunnel moves away from the tunnel in an upward direction. The above effect of likely soil displacement near the ground surface due to seismicity is more noticeable for the soil with lower ϕ value.

4.5.3 Distribution of normal stresses

Figures 4.9 and 4.10 illustrates the distribution of normal stress around the tunnel periphery for some typical cases. Here, the normal stress at each tunnel node is also normalized with γ and D . The angle reported is the angle made by the radial lines from the tunnel center with respect to the positive X axis.

Fig. 4.9(a) shows the normal stress distribution for the static loading for a square tunnel with $C/D = 1$ and for $\phi = 25^\circ$ and 40° . It is evident that the load from the earth surrounding the tunnel is symmetric about the vertical through the tunnel center, and this is indicated by the symmetric location of the maximum normal stress about that axis. Thus, even for static loading, the stress distribution may be symmetric but not uniform through the tunnel perimeter. Moreover, as ϕ increases, the normal stress onto the tunnel reduces. Fig. 4.9(b) depicts the normal stress distribution for various tunnel aspect ratios under static loading and with $\phi = 25^\circ$. The normal stresses for a narrow tunnel (B/D

FIGURE 4.9: For $C/D = 1$ and static loading, the distribution of normal stress around the tunnel periphery depicting (a) the effect of ϕ , with $\phi = 25^\circ$ and 40° , and $B/D = 1$, (b) the effect of B/D , with $B/D = 0.5, 1$ and 1.5 , and $\phi = 25^\circ$

$= 0.5$) are less than that for $B/D = 1$ and 1.5 . This re-confirms the increased stability of narrow tunnels in the perspective of distribution of normal stresses around the tunnel periphery. Another observation to be made is the shift in the location of the maximum normal stress from the vicinity of wall-roof junction for $B/D = 0.5$ and 1 to the tunnel roof for $B/D = 1.5$.

Fig. 4.10 shows the distribution of the normal stresses around the tunnel periphery for different ϕ values. Fig. 4.10(a) is plotted for $k_h = 0.1$ and Fig. 4.10(b) for $k_h = 0.2$. Also, $C/D = 1$, $B/D = 1$, and $k_v = k_h/2$ were used. Fig. 4.10 throws light on the increase in the support pressure values with k_h in Fig. 4.6. As the k_h value increases, the rise in seismic load increases the normal stresses on the tunnel nodes, thus increasing the support pressure for the tunnel.

FIGURE 4.10: For $C/D = 1$, the distribution of normal stress around the tunnel periphery for $\phi = 25^\circ, 40^\circ$ with (a) $k_h = 0.1$, and (b) $k_h = 0.2$. Here, $B/D = 1$, $k_v = k_h/2$

4.6 Validation of the present study

There seems to be no study that considers the non-uniform stress distribution around rectangular tunnel with rounded corners and seismic loading. Nevertheless, there are studies proposing the variation of the support pressure from the uniform stress distribution, σ_u (Eq. 3.25) for tunnels with sharp corners and static load. Fig. 4.11(a) shows the validation of σ_u/c from the FE-LB-LA of Wilson et al. (2015), for undrained clay of cohesion c , with the present study. Fig. 4.11(b) shows the validation of the present study with the results for Dutta and Bhattacharya (2019), for granular soil with different ϕ values, and $B/D = 1$ and 1.5. In both the cases, $C/D = 1$ and static loading were considered. The present study compares well with the results available in the literature.

In their article, Shiau et al. (2023) presented an example to compute the support pressure (considering uniform stress condition, Eq. 3.25) required for a square box culvert of size, $D = 6$ m, placed at a cover depth, $C = 18$ m in a granular soil of unit weight, $\gamma = 18$ kN/m³. Using these parameters, for $\phi = 40^\circ$, Shiau et al. (2023) reported a non-dimensional support pressure, $\sigma_u/\gamma D = 0.3140$. For the same parameters, from the present study,

FIGURE 4.11: (a) Validation of the support pressure using the uniform stress distribution (σ_u/c) from the present study for purely cohesive soil with the results from Wilson et al. (2015); (b) Validation of the support pressure $\sigma_u/\gamma D$ from the present study for granular soil with the results from Dutta and Bhattacharya (2019) for $B/D = 1$ and 1.5. Here, $C/D = 1$, static loading with sharp corners

$\sigma_u/\gamma D = 0.3146$ which differs only by 0.19%. For the same parameters, from Fig. 4.6(e), the support pressure using the non-uniform stress condition (Eq. 3.26) for $\phi = 40^\circ$ is $\sigma_s/\gamma D = 0.7499$. Hence, in the present example, comparing $\sigma_u/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, the support pressure computed using the non-uniform stress condition is about 138.36% higher than that using the uniform stress condition. To reiterate, using the support pressure from non-uniform stress condition yields a conservative tunnel design.

4.7 Summary

The stability of long square and rectangular tunnels, with rounded corners, placed in granular soil and subjected to earthquake loading was determined in the present study. The stability problem was solved using a rational approach of FE-LB-LA. The earthquake loading was considered using the well known pseudo-static method. The inertial forces were accounted for using the constant values of horizontal and vertical seismic acceleration coefficients. A typical comparison between the uniform and non-uniform stress assumption in the stresses received by the tunnel lining revealed that the support pressure found using the non-uniform stress condition led to a conservative tunnel design.

Therefore, the normal stresses were allowed to vary along the tunnel periphery, and the maximum of them was taken as the ultimate support pressure, σ_s . In the present study, the support pressure has been normalized with the unit weight (γ) and tunnel diameter (D), and expressed as $\sigma_s/\gamma D$. The effect of the interface condition between the soil and the tunnel lining has been studied and was found that the smooth interface (full slip) condition yielded conservative results. Taking into account of all these, the variation of non-dimensional support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, was reported over a range of non-dimensional parameters like C/D , B/D , k_h , k_v , and ϕ . Additionally, the nodal velocity patterns and the distribution of normal stress along the tunnel perimeter were reported for some typical cases. Furthermore, the results were compared for tunnels with sharp corners, considering the uniform stress condition, with that available in the literature.

Chapter 5

Seismic stability of rectangular tunnels in cohesive-frictional soil

5.1 Introduction

From the comprehensive literature study in Chapter 2 it was found that stability of tunnels in purely cohesive and/or cohesive-frictional soil were studied by various researchers under static loading ([Assadi and Sloan \(1991\)](#); [Lyamin et al. \(2001\)](#); [Yang and Yang \(2010\)](#); [Yamamoto et al. \(2011\)](#); [Abbo et al. \(2013\)](#); [Wilson et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Shiau et al. \(2023\)](#)) using the method of limit analysis. The response of underground structures is different to that of the structure above the ground, yet there seems to be no numerical study considering the seismic action on rectangular tunnels. Moreover, these studies consider that the surrounding soil imposes a uniform stress on the tunnel lining, but not so in reality. As stated in Chapter 4, the tunnel boring machines for rectangular tunnels seldom have sharp corners ([Li, 2017](#)).

Therefore, the present study investigates the seismic stability of square and rectangular tunnels with rounded corners in cohesive-frictional soils. Using the horizontal and vertical seismic acceleration coefficients k_h and k_v the seismic body forces were included in

the study based on the pseudo-static approach. The normal stresses along the tunnel's periphery were determined using the FE-LB-LA method; the maximum of these stresses along the tunnel periphery is the minimum pressure necessary to be resisted by the liner to maintain tunnel stability. The influence of the tunnel cover depth, aspect ratio, shear strength parameters and seismic acceleration coefficients on the support pressure has been explored along with the normal stress distribution and the collapse patterns around the tunnel.

5.2 Problem description, domain and boundary conditions

Fig. 5.1(a) shows the problem description, that is, analyzing the stability of a rectangular tunnel, with width B and depth D , placed at a cover depth C from the ground surface in a cohesive-frictional soil. Here γ is the unit weight of soil, c = cohesion of soil and ϕ is the friction angle of the soil medium. The corners of the tunnel are rounded having dimensions of b (width) and d (depth), and they vary according to the width-to-depth ratio of the tunnel (B/D). The length of the tunnel was considered to be much higher than its other dimensions, thereby facilitating the use of plane-strain condition. The seismic forces in the soil are calculated using the pseudo-static method by means of horizontal and vertical seismic acceleration coefficients, k_h and k_v , respectively. The soil is dry, homogeneous, and isotropic. The failure of soil is governed by the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion. The support pressure, σ_s , was calculated as the maximum of the normal stresses along the tunnel periphery.

A typical finite element mesh for $B/D = 1$ along with the boundary conditions for the present problem is shown in Fig. 5.1(b). No stresses were considered on the ground surface, EF; hence $\sigma_n = 0$ and $\tau = 0$ along EF. Furthermore, from 4, the support pressures are maximum when the soil-lining interaction was modeled to be smooth (full slip). Hence, $\tau = 0$ was imposed for a full slip condition along the tunnel periphery. The other boundaries, FG, GH, and EH were located far away from the tunnel center so that the support pressure

values were not affected by changing the position of boundaries further. The finite element procedure was invoked by discretizing the soil domain (EFGH) into three noded triangular elements, and the number of elements required were found to be dependent on all problem parameters.

FIGURE 5.1: (a) Problem definition, (b) A typical finite element mesh, for $B/D = 1$, and associated boundary conditions.

5.3 Comparison of uniform and non-uniform stress distributions

The magnitude of support pressures calculated considering the uniform (σ_u/c , Eqn. 3.25) and the non-uniform (σ_s/c , Eqn. 3.26) stress distributions is shown in figures 5.2(a) and (b), respectively. Here, $C/D = 1$, $k_h = 0.1$, and $k_v = kh/2$. The support pressure in either case reduce with increasing ϕ , reducing $\gamma D/c$ and B/D values. Apart from this, the support pressure calculated from the non-uniform stress distribution, Eqn. 3.26 (σ_s/c), is higher than that calculated using the uniform stress distribution, Eqn. 3.25 (σ_u/c), keeping all other parameters constant. For example, for $B/D = 1.5$, $\phi = 10^\circ$ and $\gamma D/c = 3$, the support pressure required based on the uniform stress distribution is $-0.19c$ (refer Fig. 5.2(a)). Whereas, for the same parameters but considering the maximum of the stresses from the non-uniform stress distribution, the support pressure σ_s from Fig. 5.2(b) is about $4.53c$. A negative support pressure indicates that the tunnel is self-stable. Designing the tunnel by means of the uniform distribution does not require any support pressure, but somewhere along the tunnel periphery the stresses are positive, necessitating the provision of support pressure. The same trend of σ_s/c greater than σ_u/c was observed for other parameter values also. Thus, calculating the support pressure (σ_s/c), as the maximum of the normal stress along the tunnel periphery will lead to a conservative tunnel design.

5.4 Results and Discussion

The support pressure of the tunnel, σ_s , is expressed in its normalized form as σ_s/c , and the soil parameters c and γ are considered in the normalized form as $\gamma D/c$. The soil friction angle, ϕ was varied as 5° , 10° and 20° , and the parameter $\gamma D/c$ was varied as 1, 3 and 5. The seismic forces were accounted in the analysis by considering the horizontal and vertical seismic acceleration coefficients, k_h and k_v , respectively. The values of k_h varied from zero (static) to 0.3, and $k_v = 0$ and $k_h/2$ were considered. The support pressure variations for the tunnel cover depth, aspect ratio, soil shear strength parameters, and the

FIGURE 5.2: Variation of the support pressures from the (a) uniform (σ_u/c) and (b) non-uniform (σ_s/c) stress distributions with ϕ , $\gamma D/c$ and B/D . Here, $C/D = 1$, $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$.

seismic acceleration coefficients are produced as non-dimensional charts. Apart from this, the distribution of normal stresses and the velocity distribution patterns for typical cases are presented.

5.4.1 Variation of support pressure with tunnel geometry and seismic parameters

Figures 5.3 and 5.4 show the variation of σ_s/c with B/D , k_h , k_v , ϕ and $\gamma D/c$ for $C/D = 1$ and 3, respectively. An increase in the parameter $\gamma D/c$ can be viewed as the increase in the unit weight of the soil, or increase in the depth of the tunnel, or a decrease in the cohesion of the soil. In either case, the stability of the tunnel drops, and hence the support pressure increases as $\gamma D/c$ increases. From Fig. 5.3(a), for $k_h = 0$ and $\gamma D/c = 1$, $\sigma_s = 2c$. Whereas, for the same parameters but for $\gamma D/c = 5$, $\sigma_s = 7.1c$, a steep rise by a factor of 3.55. As the friction angle of the soil increases, the shear strength of the soil increases, and hence the tunnel is more stable as ϕ increases. Therefore, the support pressure required for a tunnel in a soil with higher friction angle is less than that in a soil with low friction angle. For $k_h = 0$ and $\gamma D/c = 1$, σ_s drops by almost 50% from $2c$ for $\phi = 5^\circ$ (Fig. 5.3(a)) to $1.01c$ for $\phi = 20^\circ$ (Fig. 5.3(b)). By increasing the seismic acceleration coefficients, k_h and k_v , the body forces on each element increases. As a result, a higher support pressure

FIGURE 5.3: For $C/D = 1$, the variation of σ_s/c with k_h , k_v , $\gamma D/c$, B/D and ϕ .

is necessary to maintain the tunnel stability. From Fig. 5.3(c), for $\gamma D/c = 1$, $k_v = k_h/2$ and $k_h = 0.1$, the value of σ_s is $1.39c$, whereas for the same parameters but for $k_h = 0.3$, $\sigma_s = 2.03c$, an increase by almost 46% is observed. Also, for $\phi = 20^\circ$, $k_h = 0.3$ and $\gamma D/c = 1$, $\sigma_s = 1.61c$ for $k_v = 0$ (refer Fig. 5.3(c)). Here the support pressure for $k_v = 0$ is only about 0.8 times that for a non-zero k_v value. Thus, inclusion of the vertical seismic acceleration coefficient in the analysis yields a conservative tunnel design. The tunnel with a higher aspect ratio (B/D) has been noted to require a higher support pressure for its stability. From Fig. 5.3(c), for $B/D = 1$, $\gamma D/c = 3$, $k_h = 0.2$ and $k_v = k_h/2$, the value of σ_s is equal to $3.72c$. On the other hand, for the same parameters but for $B/D = 1.5$ (from Fig. 5.3(f)), $\sigma_s = 4.61c$ with an approximate 24% increase. The tunnel cover depth to the tunnel depth ratio (C/D) also influenced the tunnel stability for both square and rectangular tunnels. An increase in C/D value may indicate an increase in the tunnel cover depth (C) or a decrease in the tunnel depth (D). In both the cases, the stress on the tunnel increases and a higher support pressure is required. For $B/D = 1.5$, $\phi = 5^\circ$, $\gamma D/c = 5$, $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, $\sigma_s = 8c$ for $C/D = 1$ (from Fig. 5.3(d)), and $\sigma_s = 18.4c$ for $C/D = 3$ (from Fig. 5.4(d)), which is 2.3 times the support pressure for $C/D = 1$.

FIGURE 5.4: For $C/D = 3$, the variation of σ_s/c with k_h , k_v , $\gamma D/c$, B/D and ϕ .

5.4.2 Nodal velocity patterns

Figures 5.5 and 5.6 illustrate the nodal velocity patterns for a few typical cases. The MOSEK solver produces both the primal and the dual solution for the SOCP problem, the primal solution being the stresses and the dual being the nodal velocities. Fig. 5.5 is plotted for the static condition with $C/D = 1$ and $\gamma D/c = 1$. Fig. 5.5(a) is the nodal velocity pattern for $B/D = 1$ and $\phi = 5^\circ$, Fig. 5.5(b) for $B/D = 1$ and $\phi = 10^\circ$, and Fig. 5.5(c) for $B/D = 1.5$ and $\phi = 1^\circ$. At the instant of collapse, the soil mass from all the sides is noted to move towards the tunnel. This is noticed for a higher value of soil friction angle also. Furthermore, as ϕ increases, the extent of the velocity pattern around the tunnel reduces, stating that the tunnel is more stable with increasing ϕ value, as also noted in figures 5.3 and 5.4. Furthermore, as ϕ increases, the extent of the velocity pattern around the tunnel reduces, stating that the tunnel is more stable with increasing ϕ value, as in figures 5.3 and 5.4.

Fig. 5.6 is plotted for $C/D = 1$, $\phi = 5^\circ$, $k_h = 0.2$ and $k_v = k_h/2$. Fig. 5.6(a) illustrates the collapse of a square tunnel under seismic condition with $\gamma D/c = 1$. Comparing Fig. 5.5(a) and 5.6(a), as the value of k_h increases, the size of failure zone around the tunnel increases and becomes more one-sided due to seismicity. Fig. 5.6(b) is for a square tunnel with $\gamma D/c = 3$. A comparison of Fig. 5.6(b) with Fig. 5.6(a) implies that the tunnel is more prone to collapse as $\gamma D/c$ increases, which can be confirmed from the figures 5.3 and 5.4. Higher the $\gamma D/c$ value, greater is the extent of soil contributing to the tunnel collapse. Fig. 5.6(c) illustrates the collapse of a rectangular tunnel with $B/D = 1.5$ and $\gamma D/c = 3$. The nodal velocities in Fig. 5.6(c) increases in its size when compared with that from Fig. 5.6(b), indicating the reduced tunnel stability for a higher B/D ratio. Even though the collapse of both square and rectangular tunnels under seismic loading involves the movement of soil mass from all of its sides, the zone of collapse from the base increases considerably from the side of the seismic force.

5.4.3 Normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery

Figures 5.7 and 5.8 show the distribution of normal stresses at each node along the tunnel periphery. The normal stresses are expressed in non-dimensional form as σ_n/c . The angle is calculated as the angle subtended by the radial line from the tunnel center with the positive X direction. Fig. 5.7(a) shows the normal stress distribution for $\phi = 5^\circ$ and 10° by using $C/D = 3$, $B/D = 1$, and $\gamma D/c = 3$ under static loading. It is evident that when the tunnel is subjected to only static load, the distribution of the normal stress along the tunnel periphery is symmetric about the vertical through the tunnel center. Moreover, as the magnitude of ϕ rises, the tunnel is more stable, hence the normal stress on each tunnel node reduces. Therefore, the support pressure, in figures 5.3 and 5.4, reduces as ϕ increases. The distribution of σ_n/c for $C/D = 3$, $\phi = 5^\circ$, and $\gamma D/c = 5$ under static loading for $B/D = 1$ and 1.5 is shown in Fig. 5.7(b). Comparing the normal stress distribution for $\phi = 5^\circ$ from Fig. 5.7(a) and for $B/D = 1$ from Fig. 5.7(b), it can be noted that the normal stress increases as the value of $\gamma D/c$ increases. Such an

FIGURE 5.5: For $C/D = 1$ and $\gamma D/c = 1$, the nodal velocity patterns under static loading with (a) $B/D = 1$, $\phi = 5^\circ$, (b) $B/D = 1$, $\phi = 10^\circ$, and (c) $B/D = 1.5$, $\phi = 10^\circ$.

FIGURE 5.6: For $C/D = 1$, $\phi = 5^\circ$, the nodal velocity patterns for seismic loading with (a) $B/D = 1$, $\gamma D/c = 1$, (b) $B/D = 1$, $\gamma D/c = 3$, and (c) $B/D = 1.5$, $\gamma D/c = 3$. Here, $k_h = 0.2$ and $k_v = k_h/2$.

increase in the normal stress at all the tunnel nodes, as $\gamma D/c$ increases, is the reason for the increase in the support pressure values in figures 5.3 and 5.4. From Fig. 5.7(b), apart from the distribution being symmetric as before, the location of the normal stress shifts from the vicinity of the tunnel corner for a square tunnel to the tunnel roof for the rectangular tunnel. This reinforces the fact that the rectangular tunnel under static loading, is vulnerable to roof collapse than the tunnel wall collapse.

Fig. 5.8 shows the distribution of σ_n/c for seismic loading with $C/D = 3$, $B/D = 1$, $\phi = 5^\circ$ and $k_v = k_h/2$, and for $\gamma D/c = 3$ and 5. Fig. 5.8(a) shows the normal stress distribution for $k_h = 0.1$, and Fig. 5.8(b) for $k_h = 0.2$. By comparing the normal stress distribution for $\phi = 5^\circ$ from Fig. 5.7(a) and the σ_n/c distribution for $\gamma D/c = 3$ from Fig. 5.8(a), it is clear that as the seismicity is introduced, the normal stress distribution gets skewed along the direction of the seismic loading. Moreover, as k_h increases, the normal stress on each tunnel node increases, thereby increasing the support pressure required for tunnel stability, which is noticeable from figures 5.8(a) and 5.8(b). Apart from the above, the increase in the normal stresses, and thus the support pressure, due to rise in the value of $\gamma D/c$ is also evident from Fig. 5.8.

FIGURE 5.7: For $C/D = 3$ and static loading, the distribution of normal stresses around the tunnel periphery for (a) different ϕ values with $B/D = 1$ and $\gamma D/c = 3$, and (b) different B/D values with $\phi = 5^\circ$ and $\gamma D/c = 5$.

5.5 Validation of the present study

To the best of authors' knowledge, there exists no study reporting the non-uniform stress distribution around the tunnel under seismic conditions for square or rectangular tunnel with rounded corners. Nonetheless, there are studies considering the uniform stress

FIGURE 5.8: For $C/D = 3$, $B/D = 1$, and $\phi = 5^\circ$, the variation of normal stresses along the tunnel periphery for $\gamma D/c = 3$ and 5 with (a) $k_h = 0.1$, and (b) $k_h = 0.2$. Here, $k_v = k_h/2$.

distribution around the tunnel (Eqn. 3.25) under static loading for tunnels with sharp corners (Yang and Yang, 2010; Abbo et al., 2013). Fig. 5.9(a) compares the support pressure, σ_u/c , from the present study with the results of Yang and Yang (2010) for square tunnels in cohesive frictional soils. It is to be noted that the results from Yang and Yang (2010) are by using the UB finite element limit analysis method, whereas the present method employs the finite element lower bound method. The comparison of σ_u/c from the present study with that of Abbo et al. (2013) for different values of B/D and $\gamma D/c$ is depicted in Fig. 5.9(b). The results from the present study are noted to be in-line with the literature available.

5.6 Summary

The seismic stability of square and rectangular tunnels, with rounded corners, in a cohesive-frictional soil has been studied using the finite element lower bound limit analysis method. The seismic inertial forces along the horizontal and the vertical directions were considered using the corresponding pseudo-static acceleration coefficients. The uniform

FIGURE 5.9: Validation of the support pressure from the uniform stress distribution of the present study with (a) the upper bound results of [Yang and Yang \(2010\)](#) for cohesive-frictional soil with $\gamma D/c$, and (b) the lower bound results of [Abbo et al. \(2013\)](#) for purely cohesive soil with $C/D = 3$ and various $\gamma D/c$ values. Here, static loading along with sharp corners were considered.

Note: LB-FELA – Lower Bound-Finite Element Limit Analysis, and UB-FELA – Upper Bound- Finite Element Limit Analysis.

stress condition that imposes a constraint that the normal stress along the tunnel periphery needs to be equal was not considered in the present study. As a result, the normal stress varied along the tunnel boundary. Therefore, the maximum normal stress from all the tunnel boundary nodes was reported as the minimum support pressure, σ_s , required to ensure tunnel stability. For an improved applicability to different field conditions, the results were presented in the form of non-dimensional charts showing the variation of the dimensionless support pressure, σ_s/c . Owing to the conservative results, the support pressure was reported only for the smooth interface condition between soil and the tunnel lining. The present study was validated by generating results for tunnels with sharp corners and imposing the constraint of equal normal stress along the tunnel periphery.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

6.1 General

In the present thesis, the seismic stability of square and rectangular tunnels under two different ground conditions were studied. The ground conditions considered in this thesis were granular and cohesive-frictional soils. The method of lower bound limit analysis along with the finite element discretization technique was used to solve the problem of tunnel stability. The shape of the tunnels considered were close to the shape of a real, rectangular tunnel boring machine with the incorporation of rounded corners. The inertial forces along the horizontal and vertical directions, induced by the earthquake motion, were accounted for using the corresponding pseudo-static body forces. The constraint of equal normal stress at all the nodes along the tunnel periphery was not included in the study so that the normal stresses vary through out the tunnel perimeter. Thus, the ultimate support pressure required to maintain the tunnel stability was taken as the maximum normal stress along the tunnel periphery. The aspect ratio of the tunnel was varied to study its effect. The non-dimensional charts provided in this thesis can be readily applied by the field engineers for the safe design of rectangular underground structures placed in either granular or cohesive-frictional soil.

6.2 Conclusions

From the works done in the current thesis, following conclusions could be obtained:

- The support pressure required for the tunnel stability is higher while considering the non-uniform stress distribution in comparison with the uniform stress distribution assumption, thus leading to a conservative tunnel design.
- The smooth interface between the tunnel lining and the surrounding earth, indicated by $\delta/\phi = 0$, provided higher support pressure than the rough interface.
- Due to the higher overburden stress, the tunnels with a larger cover depth-to-tunnel depth ratio (C/D) required higher support pressure. Moreover, the support pressure requirement increases with the tunnel's aspect ratio, B/D .
- The support pressure was found to increase with the seismic acceleration coefficients (k_h and k_v). The reason can be because of the increased seismic body force for higher values of k_h and k_v . Furthermore, a non-zero value of k_v resulted in a higher support pressure.
- The nodal velocity patterns were found to be influenced by the cover depth, soil's strength parameters and the tunnel aspect ratio (B/D). It was found that the value of B/D had a higher influence on the nodal velocity pattern. From the nodal velocity patterns, it was found that the collapse of the narrow tunnel was to the collapse of its walls. Whereas, for a wide tunnel, the downward soil movement from the roof and the upward soil movement from the base contributed more towards the tunnel collapse. For a square tunnel, the collapse involved the collapse of its roof, walls, and base.
- Under seismic loading, the nodal velocity pattern was one-sided apart from increasing in its size. The movement of soil mass from all the sides of tunnels was involved along with substantial increase at the base from the side of the seismic force.

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- The normal stress distribution patterns were symmetric for static loading, and otherwise for seismic loading.
 - The normal stress along the tunnel perimeter increased with k_h , B/D , and C/D . Furthermore, the normal stress' magnitude was influenced by the soil's shear strength. For granular soils, it increased for a lower ϕ value. On the other hand, for a cohesive-frictional soil, the magnitude of normal stress increased for a lower ϕ and higher $\gamma D/c$ values.
 - The normal stress along the tunnel periphery was higher for higher values of k_h , B/D , and lower ϕ values. The location of the maximum normal stress shifted from the vicinity of wall-roof junction to the tunnel roof for a wide rectangular tunnel.
 - The location of the maximum normal stress shifted from near the tunnel corners for a square tunnel to the tunnel roof for a rectangular tunnel.

Chapter 7

Scope for future work

The current chapter discusses the direction along which the present research can be extended to address or to include most appropriate and contemporary enhancements.

Use of other dynamic methods In the present study, the seismic inertial forces were accounted using the pseudo-static method. This method considers the seismic body forces using the seismic acceleration coefficients along the horizontal and vertical directions. The actual earthquake motion shows a spatio-temporal variation in its magnitude. On the contrary, the pseudo-static method considers a constant seismic acceleration in terms of the acceleration coefficients. Thus, the pseudo-static body forces do not vary with time and space. Furthermore, the amplification to the seismic acceleration caused by the local soil conditions need to accounted for while calculating the seismic body forces, along with satisfying the traction boundary conditions at the ground surface. Therefore, the seismic stability of rectangular tunnels using other dynamic methods like the conventional pseudo-dynamic, spectral pseudo-dynamic, and the modified pseudo-dynamic methods can be undertaken.

The non-associated flow rule and an enhanced yield criteria It is known that the associated flow rule is more applicable for undrained conditions. For the drained loading conditions, the results obtained from the associated flow rule is generally higher than the actual result owing to the excessive dilation angle. However, as per the suggestions by [Davis \(1968\)](#) and [Drescher and Detournay \(1993\)](#), the equivalent shear strength parameters of the soil with a known dilation angle can be used to compute the results for the case of non-associated plasticity. The Lade yield criterion, proposed by [Lade \(1977\)](#) for granular soils, can be formulated in principal stress space which can be used for interpreting equally well triaxial and plane strain tests.

Miscellaneous The present research considered the soil to be isotropic and homogeneous. In reality, the soil is seldom isotropic and homogeneous. Therefore, the present work can be extended to consider these field conditions. The anisotropy in the soil friction angle can be modeled using the equivalent friction angle given by [Meyerhof \(1978\)](#). A more recent and a rational approach of modeling the inherently anisotropic granular soil using the fabric tensor under the FE-LB-LA was proposed by [Veiskarami and Shokoohi \(2023\)](#) and applied to the bearing capacity problem. The present research could be easily modified to adopt the development by [Veiskarami and Shokoohi \(2023\)](#) and produce the support pressure required by the tunnels in inherently anisotropic granular soil under seismic loading.

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